

PROSPECTS OF DIGITAL LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. This article provides some ideas about what the digitalization of education is and how the pandemic has affected educational institutions around the world, as well as how students, educators and entrepreneurs can benefit from future educational technologies.

Keywords: pandemic, education, digital technology, educational technology, integration, digital education, distance education.

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ЦИФРОВЫХ ОБУЧАЮЩИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

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Аннотация. В этой статье представлены некоторые идеи о том, что такое цифровизация образования и как пандемия повлияла на образовательные учреждения по всему миру, а также какую выгоду студенты, преподаватели и предприниматели могут извлечь из будущих образовательных технологий.

Ключевые слова: пандемия, образование, цифровая технология, образовательная технология, интеграция, цифровая образование, дистанционная образование.

The digital age has changed all aspects of our lives. It will define how we live, work, travel, communicate and more importantly, it will change the way we learn and be educated. The 2020 COVID 19 pandemic has put the global education system

to the test, revealing a number of its gaps and problems, revealing the practical importance of digital education technologies.

With the world under strict quarantine rules, the need to digitize the education sector has become vital. Although the closure of colleges and universities has had a severe impact on traditional education systems, they have been able to overcome the difficult situation with digital educational tools. In fact, pandemic restrictions have dramatically increased demand for digital learning technologies in general. The unique advantages of digitization of education have been highlighted. Literacy of digital technologies in the part of the population working in the field of education has increased significantly.

Digitization of education in the world not only creates an opportunity to spread knowledge and information around the world, but also opens the door to opportunities such as sharing information and experience. If we dwell on the advantages of digitization in educational institutions today, first of all, the availability of large amounts of information and data saves students from spending hours searching for the necessary information, most importantly, it saves time, allows you to significantly speed up the educational process, in addition, the digital environment between students from different regions of the world encourages cooperation, facilitates the exchange of ideas. Secondly, digitization of education allows the student to choose any convenient time of the day for education, while giving students the opportunity to access the information they are interested in when they need it most, it fills the gaps in their knowledge and increases their creativity. Thirdly, through digital education, students will be provided with the opportunity to get quality education at affordable prices, students will not need to attend an educational institution, live in student housing and rent, and social structures that serve them. Most importantly, money and time are saved. Fourthly, the teacher, who is considered the main subject of education, is freed from conducting lessons, checking homework, planning lessons, performing administrative tasks, and gives the prospect of spending his talent and potential on improving educational programs

or starting new projects. Modern learning management systems (LMS) help teachers check homework, administer tests, plan future lessons, assign grades, and more. Digital technologies can take the burden of control off the shoulders of teachers, allowing them to focus on teaching rather than serving a bureaucratic system.

Despite the obvious benefits of digitization for education, there are a number of inherent problems of digitization that must be addressed. First of all, there are limited technical capabilities, poor quality of service electronic devices or limited service availability, lack of access to the Internet, lack of information technology specialists, and the financial situation is also very poor. Secondly, it is necessary to abandon the stereotype that electronic education cannot replace traditional education, and thirdly, despite all the advantages of digital education, this technology still cannot replace people (teachers), although well-structured educational content helps students absorb and process information faster, but Personal communication is important for students to develop certain skills. Fourthly, new technologies are always accompanied by changes, and not all people are ready to accept these changes. Some university professors may not be ready for change, and may prefer traditional methods that have been proven. Fear of newness is human nature and common to many people. However, it is important that teachers take the initiative and motivate students. Educators should be the first to master new digital educational technologies. They should have all the information that shows how the use of modern digital tools can benefit students. Fifth, digital education requires the introduction of standardized protocols and procedures by the state. The lack of a general approach makes it difficult to analyze the field of education. Without clear rules, each learner will try to come up with their own version or simply copy what has worked well for others. Therefore, clear criteria or standards should be established.

Based on the above, it is necessary to pay attention to the following three aspects:

- to support the optimization and updating of educational resources;

- increase the information literacy of teachers and students;
- scientific decision-making in the field of education management, systematization of public services and standardization of management;
- deepening the integration of digital technologies and education.

The integration and development of information technology and education is an upward moving process. The most important thing is that the sooner digital technologies are introduced into the education system of our country, the better the quality and success of the reforms will be.

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